

ENTECH

entechonline.com

ISSN (Online): 2584-2749

April 2026

VOLUME-4

ISSUE-4

**Power-Packed
Green Nanoparticles**

**Intelligent Systems
Beyond ML Models**

**Personalized Learning
Unique AI Path for Everyone**

**Curated App
Qustodio**

**Collaborative Intelligence
Future Skills**

Table of Contents

- 09** **Power-packed and Potent: The Sustainability Potential of Green Nanoparticles**
Dr. Subhadip Senapati and Manaswini Vijayakumar
- 14** **Engineering Intelligent Systems: Beyond ML Models**
Piyusha Patil
- 21** **Personalized Learning with AI: Unique Path for Every Student**
Raj Kumar Mahto
- 27** **India's STEM Moment: Are We Ready for an AI-Driven Future?**
Aryan Srivastava
- 33** **Incident Orchestration and Multi-Step Problem Solving with AI**
Srikanth Madabhushi
- 37** **Why Does Time Slow Down When You Are Scared?**
Juveriya Khan
- 43** **Should We Invest More in Space Exploration or Fix Problems on Earth? The Big Question**
Sadaf Lone
- 47** **Qustodio App: A Smart Way to Support Kids Online**
Venkat Raghava
- 52** **Collaborative Intelligence: Working in Mixed-Reality Teams**
Deven Nandapurkar
- 56** **Time Capsule: April**
Shreem Mishra
- 62** **Top 10 STEM Discoveries and Innovations of March 2026**

> **JOB ROLES FOR 2030**

Power-packed and Potent: The Sustainability Potential of Green Nanoparticles

Written By:

Dr. Subhadip Senapati & Manaswini Vijayakumar

A billionth of a meter, 80,000 making up a single strand of human hair; nanoparticles are tiny powerhouses whose strength is disproportionate to their size. At the cutting-edge of science today, nanomaterials are miniatures that find applications across waste management, renewable energy, sensors, pharmaceuticals and biomedicine.

While they are more sensitive, effective, and targeted than their normal sized counterparts, nanomaterials also guzzle a lot of energy and raw material. Most times, synthesizing them requires toxic chemicals, extreme temperature or pressure, and the process also releases byproducts that are hazardous and non-biodegradable.

Green Nanomaterials: Nature meets Nano

There exists then a toss-up between the enhanced efficacy of nanomaterials vis-a-vis environmental and energy costs of their production. In response, scientists are now increasingly shifting towards a greener paradigm that contributes to the sustainability of effort.

So green nanomaterials seem like a dream! What's holding them back?

“Green” nanomaterials are so labelled because their production involves eco-friendly biological methods in aqueous media, primarily from natural sources like plants and microbes, avoiding harsh chemicals and toxic solvents. This “Safe and sustainable by Design (SSbD)” approach ensures that from raw materials and manufacturing to disposal, all aspects of producing these nanoparticles are environmentally friendly, requiring minimal energy throughout.

Diverse Types and Biological Sources of Green Nanomaterials

Green Nanomaterials produced can be of different types, that utilize distinct raw materials. For example, there are metal and metal oxide nanomaterials, graphene oxides, carbon nanoparticles, and polymeric nanoparticles to name a few. Metal nanoparticles are often synthesized using natural raw materials such as fruit peels, neem, turmeric and cellulose.

The resultant nanoparticles often have biological, environmental, and material science applications and can be used across different industries. Silver nanoparticles are the most popular in this regard.

Advanced Applications of Green Nanomaterials in Biomedicine and Industry

Likewise, biomass can also be used to produce carbon nanoparticles like carbon quantum dots (CQDs) that have extensive application in biomedicine. Their fluorescence properties can help visualize cells and track tumor growth for instance, while staving off the heavy metal toxicity that comes with conventional CQDs. This property can also help in developing anti-counterfeiting inks for currency note evaluation. Nanocellulose and chitosan are polymeric nanofibers that can mimic human tissue paving the way for regenerative medicines like artificial skin and cartilage repair.

The Green Brick Road Ahead

In the past few years, people have made progress in creating the next generation of green nanoparticles. They use more sustainable, eco-friendly, less toxic, and energy-saving methods. Initially begun with plant extracts, and later with microorganisms, green synthesis in recent years has been increasingly utilizing pure compounds, peptides and proteins, enzymes, and waste materials. Recent research focus on green nanoparticles has shifted toward bionanocomposites—multifunctional, stimuli-responsive, nanozymes, and carbon-based nano-hybrids. Scalable and reproducible outcomes, potentially supplemented by artificial intelligence, will dictate the future of green nanotechnology. The promises shown by the initial data may play critical roles in sustainable solutions in the field of materials science, environmental, and medicinal applications.

An eco-paradox

Nature is inherently diverse—no one molecule will ever be or behave like the other. When creating nanoparticles from such “clean” sources, this variability translates into the application. Inherent variability means you cannot standardize outcomes; this lack of uniformity prevents an industrial workflow from functioning at scale. This is especially true of medical applications where predictability is of prime importance. Consistency and quality fluctuate across batches; production requires consumption of large quantities of energy and water, and quick spoilage is a thorn in the side of this alternative process.

Yet their diminutive size has a flip side too.

These particles can easily pass into the bloodstream, enter the lungs through inhalation, and accumulate in organs. Many studies try to understand their harm. But without long-term studies, dangers may still exist. In the meantime, industries should use protective gear and add ventilation systems. Regulatory agencies must invest on strict studies of exposure and life-cycle checks. These will show the possible health effects.

While we use AI to understand the brain, we are also using the brain to build better AI. This is called Neuromorphic Computing.

References:

1. Green Synthesis of Nanoparticles – AAPS Newsmagazine. (n.d.). Higher Logic, LLC. <https://www.aapsnewsmagazine.org/aapsnewsmagazine/articles/new-page2/jan24/cover-story-jan24>
2. AZoNano. (2024, September 6). Green nanoparticles: a promising solution against antibiotic resistance. <https://www.azonano.com/news.aspx?newsID=41042>
3. Ferdush J, Rahman MM, Parvez MMH, Mohotadi MAA, Uddin MN. Green-Synthesized Nanomaterials for Water Disinfection: Mechanisms, Efficacy, and Environmental Safety. *Nanomaterials*. 2025; 15(19):1507. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano15191507>
4. Raul, P. K., Santra, P., Goswami, D., Tyagi, V., Yellappa, C., Mauka, V., Devi, R. R., Chattopadhyay, P., Jayaram, R. V., & Dwivedi, S. K. (2021). Green synthesis of carbon dot silver nanohybrids from fruits and vegetable’s peel waste: Applications as potent mosquito larvicide. *Current Research in Green and Sustainable Chemistry*, 4, 100158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crgsc.2021.100158>
5. Sharma, D., & Hussain, C. M. (2018). Smart nanomaterials in pharmaceutical analysis. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 13(1), 3319–3343. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arabjc.2018.11.007>
6. Liu Q, Chen H, Mi R, Min X, Fang M, Wu X, Huang Z, Liu Y. Biomass-Derived Carbon Dots: Preparation, Properties, and Applications. *Nanomaterials*. 2025; 15(16):1279. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano15161279>

Dr. Subhadip Senapati

Dr. Subhadip Senapati is a Lead Researcher at Prayoga Institute of Education Research. Upon completing his M.Sc. from IITM, he earned his Ph.D. from Arizona State University in 2015 under the guidance of Dr. Stuart Lindsay. Later, he pursued postdoctoral training under Dr. Paul S.-H. Park at Case Western Reserve University.

At present, he is working on several academic and industrial challenges focused on green chemistry, biochemistry, sustainability, and nanoscience.

subhadip.senapati@prayoga.org.in

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/subhadip-senapati-32872640/>

Manaswini Vijayakumar

Manaswini is the Lead-Communications & Community Engagement at AssisTech Foundation (ATF).

She has previously worked as a science communications professional at Prayoga Institute of Education Research. In this capacity, she has written pieces across different areas in green chemistry, earth sciences, nanomaterials, and many others, seeking to situate scientific research in the context of social development.

manaswinivijayakumar@gmail.com

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/manaswini-vijayakumar-89101935b/>